

Western Blot Image Processing

The following images were used to make the HOG1 western blot figure. These are original scans from the LiCor fluorescence gel scanner (Image Studio software) that were exported as dual channel images.

- S288C (top gel in panel A; all stresses at 5 min):
hog1_rep1_phosphop38green_9p5_actinred_7p5_dmock5_dnacl5_dh2025_detoh5_mmock5_mnacl5_mh2025_metoh5_ladder_fulllad_bw.tif
- YPS606 (middle gel in panel A; all stresses at 5 min):
hog1_rep1_phosphop38green_9p5_actinred_7p5_ladder_ymock5_ynacl5_yh2025_yetoh5_fulllad_bw.tif
- M22 (bottom gel in panel A; all stresses at 5 min):
hog1_rep1_phosphop38green_9p5_actinred_7p5_dmock5_dnacl5_dh2025_detoh5_mmock5_mnacl5_mh2025_metoh5_ladder_fulllad_bw.tif
same gel as for S288C above
- Peroxide timecourse (both left gels in panel B; S288C and YPS606 at 30 and 60 min):
hog1_rep2_phosphop38green_10_actinred_7p5_ymock5_ynacl5_yh2o25_yetoh5_dh2o230_dh2o260_yh20230_yh2o260_fulllad_bw.tif
- Ethanol timecourse (both right gels in panel B; S288C and YPS606 at 30 and 60 min):
hog1_rep3_phosphop38green_10_actinred_5_ymock30_ymock60_yetoh30_yetoh60_detoh30_detoh60_partlad_bw_bright_green_2.tif

Original scans were manipulated as follows:

1. Images were opened in Photoshop and converted to greyscale. This removes the blue color for the saturated pixels.
2. Images were rotated so that bands were perfectly lined up horizontally, if necessary.
3. Brightness and contrast were adjusted across the entire image for gels where globally, bands were faint or background was high. Care was taken to ensure no bands were lost or obscured with the adjustment.
4. Images were cropped to specific bands for each panel and images were saved as new files in Cropped Images folder.
 - a. For 4 lane images, crop box size was 1.4" wide x 0.4" tall.
 - b. For 2 lane images, crop box size was 0.7" wide x 0.4" tall.
5. Cropped images were imported into Illustrator and arranged into final figure.
6. Each image was embedded into the Illustrator file and rasterized to 300 dpi.

Microscopy Image Processing

The microscopy figure was created from the following original microscope scans:

- DBY no stress: 061424-DBY-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-No_stress.czi
- DBY NaCl: 071224-DBY-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-NaCl_1_02.czi
- DBY H2O2: 061824-DBY-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-H2O2_1_04.czi
- DBY EtOH: 071224-DBY-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-EtOH_1_02.czi
- YPS606 no stress: 073024-YPS606-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-No_stress_1_03.czi
- YPS606 NaCl: 073024-YPS606-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-NaCl_1_03.czi
- YPS606 H2O2: 070924-YPS606-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-H2O2_1_04.czi
- YPS606 EtOH: 073024-YPS606-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-EtOH_1_03.czi
- M22 no stress: 071624-M22-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-No_stress_1_02.czi
- M22 NaCl: 071624-M22-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-NaCl_1_03.czi
- M22 H2O2: 071624-M22-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-H2O2_1_02.czi
- M22 EtOH: 072624-M22-Hog1GFP_DAPI-20x_4x-EtOH_1_03.czi

Each original microscopy image (8-bit; 1024x1024) was manipulated with the same steps as follows:

1. Each .czi file was opened in Fiji (ImageJ 1.54p) with “split channels” selected to generate a separate image for the DAPI and GFP channels. The DAPI channel was not used for figure generation and was discarded. The GFP channel image was false-colored as green by the software’s default settings. All further manipulations were done with the GFP channel only image.
2. The brightness of each GFP image was adjusted to following settings (range 8-bit 0-225):

Image	original scan setting		adjusted final settings	
	min	max	min	max
DBY no stress	0	38	0	20
DBY NaCl	0	222	0	160
DBY H2O2	0	51	0	40
DBY EtOH	0	109	0	90
YPS606 no stress	0	141	0	120
YPS606 NaCl	0	209	0	170
YPS606 H2O2	0	127	0	127
YPS606 EtOH	0	139	0	110
M22 no stress	0	134	0	125
M22 NaCl	0	236	0	210
M22 H2O2	0	108	0	90
M22 EtOH	0	131	0	110

To ensure no part of the image was distorted, obscured, or otherwise changed by the brightness adjustment, the GFP image was duplicated and only one copy was adjusted. The images were visually scrutinized side-by-side on the screen to ensure there was no difference between the two images.

3. Images were smoothed (Process → Smooth).
4. Adjusted images were changed to RGB color and saved as .tiff images in the sub-folder titled: Tiffs for figure. New filenames are: Strain Condition.tiff.
5. Images were placed into Illustrator (using place function), then embedded.
6. For the first image (S288C control), the microscope scan that was done including a scale bar (4x Scan Zoom - Scale_Bar_Reference.jpg) was also placed in the Illustrator document. This scan was done at the same resolution and size (1024x1024 with 10x objective and 4x zoom) as all the images in the figure. The line tool in Illustrator was used to draw a line of the exact same size as the reference image to create a new scale bar that can be moved in Illustrator. The new scale bar was moved onto the S288C control image and they were grouped.
7. All images were scaled to 8%. The scale bar in the first figure scaled proportionally since it was grouped with the image.
8. To zoom in images, each image was cropped to 1.4 x 1.4 cm (size was halved). Then, images were doubled in size to 2.8 x 2.8 cm (2x zoom, effectively).
9. Images were rasterized to 300 ppi (RGB color mode).